

Kinetics of Decarboxylation of Malonic Acid and Substituted Malonic Acids in Molten State and Liquid Crystal Solvent*

MIHIR K. BISWAS and DILIP K. MAJUMDAR

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235, West Bengal

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Rates of decarboxylation of malonic and substituted malonic acids, methylmalonic acid, dimethylmalonic acid, ethylmalonic acid and benzylmalonic acids in molten state have been followed at several temperatures by measuring the volume of CO_2 evolved at various times. Employing Eyring equation, the thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated. Decarboxylation kinetics of malonic acid in liquid crystal solvent is also reported.

KINETIC studies have been reported previously on decarboxylation of malonic^{1,2,4} benzylmalonic³ and hexylmalonic acids⁵ in the molten state by Hinshelwood and Clark. The present paper reports the results of kinetic studies on decarboxylation of malonic acid and some substituted malonic acids, namely, methylmalonic, ethylmalonic and dimethylmalonic acids in molten state and of malonic acid in a liquid crystal solvent, i.e., *p*-azoxyanisole.

In our recent publication⁴ we reported on the results of our investigation into the kinetics of decarboxylation of malonic acid, methylmalonic acids⁶, substituted malonic acids⁶ in hydroxylic solvents, namely, alkane diols and diethylene-, polyethylene- and polypropylene glycols. Studies on the decarboxylation of the free acids in molten state will provide a better understanding of the decarboxylation process.

Experimental

Materials: Malonic acid (Reidal, Germany). Benzyl-, Methyl-, Ethyl- and Dimethylmalonic acids (Fluka AG, Switzerland), *p*-azoxyanisole (Koch Light, England). The acid sample was taken in a small bulb of about 2 ml capacity, which was connected to the gas burette through a capillary tube.

Rates were determined by collecting CO_2 gas in the gas burette over an aqueous solution⁴ prepared by mixing 20% by weight of sodium sulphate and 5% by volume of sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) coloured with methyl red. Temperature was controlled in a thermostat within $\pm 0.2^\circ$. Heavy grade liquid paraffin was used as the bath liquid.

The gas burette was surrounded by a wider jacket through which water at room temperature was circulated. In each set of experiment the amount of acid was approximately 0.17 g excepting benzylmalonic acid for which the amount was approximately 0.105 g. In the liquid crystal solvent,

the amount of malonic acid taken was about 0.08 g in ~ 0.5 g *p*-azoxyanisole.

Results and Discussion

Decarboxylation in molten state: The decarboxylation was studied at three temperatures over approximately a 10° temperature interval. A plot of $\log (V_\infty - V_t)$ vs time t was linear over practically the entire course of the reaction. V_∞ and V_t represent the volume of CO_2 gas when the reaction was completed and at time t respectively. The rate constants were calculated in the usual manner from the slopes of the experimental logarithmic plot and are given in Table 1 (A and B).

TABLE 1 (A AND B)—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT FOR DECARBOXYLATION OF MALONIC AND SUBSTITUTED MALONIC ACIDS

Acid	TABLE A				
	Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)				
	Rate constants $\times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$				
	180	141	146	151	156
1. Malonic	—	3.92	8.82	13.20	20.47
2. Benzylmalonic	2.37	7.10	—	16.73	—
3. Methylmalonic	1.93	5.12	—	16.91	—
4. Ethylmalonic	1.21	3.98	—	10.48	—

Acid	TABLE (B)		
	Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)		
	Rate constants $\times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$		
	192	200	210
Dimethylmalonic	7.19	16.02	28.64

It was also observed that a plot of $\ln (k_r/T)$ against $1/T$ is linear over the temperatures 130-151 $^\circ$ for all these acids in the molten state (Fig. 1).

* A preliminary report of a portion of this work was presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists, held in October, 1979 at Kurukshetra University, India.

Fig. 1. A plot of $\ln k_r/T$ vs $1/T$ for the decarboxylation of malonic and substituted malonic acids in molten state and of malonic acid in *p*-azoxyanisole. $\circ$, $\otimes$, $\circ$, $\bullet$ and Δ refer to decarboxylation of malonic acid, benzylmalonic acid, ethylmalonic acid, methylmalonic acid and dimethylmalonic acid in the molten state respectively. Δ refers to the decarboxylation of malonic acid in *p*-azoxyanisole.

Based on equation (1)

$$k_r = \frac{kT}{h} \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta H^\ddagger}{RT}\right) \exp(\Delta S^\ddagger/R) \quad \dots (1)$$

the values of the enthalpy of activation $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and entropy of activation $\Delta S^\ddagger$ were evaluated from the slopes and the intercepts. In eq (1) k_r is the rate constant at $T^\circ\text{K}$, h is Planck's constant, R molar gas constant and k is the Boltzmann constant.

Knowing the values of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$, the values of free energy of activation $\Delta F^\ddagger$ at the respective melting points of the acids were evaluated using equation (2).

$$\Delta F^\ddagger = \Delta H^\ddagger - T\Delta S^\ddagger \quad \dots (2)$$

The thermodynamic parameters $\Delta H^\ddagger$; $\Delta S^\ddagger$ and $\Delta F^\ddagger$ are listed in Table 2. The values of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are average over the temperature range studied.

The high $\Delta H^\ddagger$ may be attributed to the relatively weak electron attracting power of the acids. The values of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ are nearly the same for all the acids; the entropy of activation $\Delta S^\ddagger$, however, has very low values for benzyl- and dimethylmalonic acids.

It is established that decarboxylation of malonic acid⁴ follows a first order in solvents like alkane

TABLE 2—DECARBOXYLATION OF MALONIC AND SUBSTITUTED MALONIC ACIDS IN MOLTEN STATE. THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Acid	Enthalpy of activation $\Delta H^\ddagger$ (Kcal.mole ⁻¹)	Entropy of activation $\Delta S^\ddagger$ (cal. deg. ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹)	Free energy of activation $\Delta F^\ddagger$ at the respective melting points (Kcal. mole ⁻¹)
1. Malonic	32.7	8.5	29.2
2. Benzylmalonic	35.8 ^a	11.9 ^a	
	29.40	- 2.31	30.31
	29.4 ^a	- 2.6 ^a	
3. Methylmalonic	33.58	7.15	30.72
4. Ethylmalonic	34.11	7.61	31.19
5. Dimethylmalonic	33.55	3.65	32.14

^a The data of Clark (ref. 2).

diols, polyethylene-, polypropylene- and diethylene glycols. As the decarboxylation of the molten acid also follows a first order rate equation, it was supposed⁷ that a complex is formed by co-ordination between the carbonyl-carbon atom of one molecule of acid and the unshared pair of electrons on the hydroxyl oxygen atom of another molecule. The two species, electrophilic and nucleophilic, exist as associated complexes of two or more molecules each^{8, 9}.

Investigations into the reaction $\text{HA}^- + \text{DA}^- \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{A}^-$ by the temperature jump and potentiometric titration methods led Miles and co-workers¹¹ to believe that malonic acid and substituted malonic acids are intramolecularly hydrogen bonded. A mechanism similar to that suggested for the decarboxylation of β -keto acids is that the decarboxylation of undissociated malonic acid proceeds through a hydrogen bonded structure⁹.

R_1 and R_2 are alkyl substituents or H.

Decarboxylation of malonic acid in p-azoxyanisole : The decarboxylation kinetics of malonic acid in the nematic and isotropic phases of *p*-azoxyanisole at 123°, 135° and 140° was also measured. A plot of $\log(V_\infty - V_t)$ vs time t as shown in Fig. 2, is linear at any temperature between 123°-140°. This shows that the decarboxylation follows a first order rate equation in *p*-azoxyanisole solvent too. The plot of $\ln k_r/T$ against $1/T$ is linear through nematic to isotropic phases of the solvent (Fig. 1). The rate constants and the relevant thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 3. *p*-Azoxyanisole is a liquid crystal having clearance temperature 134° and nematic phase extending from 116°-134°. The decarboxylation rate constant of malonic acid at

Fig. 2. Decarboxylation kinetics of malonic acid in *p*-azoxyanisole: A plot of $\log(V_{\infty} - V_t)$ vs time t , at different temperatures. $\otimes$, $\odot$ and $\circ$ refer to decarboxylation of malonic acid in *p*-azoxyanisole at 123°, 135° and 140° respectively.

TABLE 3—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE DECARBOXYLATION OF MALONIC ACID IN *p*-AZOXYANISOLE

Temperature °C	Rate constants (kr) $\hat{k}r \times 10^4$ sec ⁻¹	Thermodynamic parameters		
		Enthalpy of activation $\Delta H^\ddagger$ K cal. mole ⁻¹	Entropy of activation $\Delta S^\ddagger$ cal. deg ⁻¹ . mole ⁻¹	Free energy of activation $\Delta F^\ddagger$ 135° K cal. mole ⁻¹
123	2.19			
135	4.70	29.1	-2.5	30.1
140	10.12			

141° is $3.92 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, while it is $10.12 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ in *p*-azoxyanisole at the same temperature. At comparable temperature $\sim 140^\circ$ in hydroxylic solvents⁴ too, the decarboxylation rate constant is of an order similar to that in *p*-azoxyanisole. It is noted that the rate constants are not significantly different from those observed in isotropic solvents. If the decarboxylation proceeds via hydrogen bonded intermediates, both in the nematic and isotropic solvents, it is but natural to expect similar value for the activation parameters and rate constants. Similar conclusions were reached by Bacon¹⁰ on the rates of intramolecular Claisen rearrangements of para substituted alkyl phenyl ethers in nematic and isotropic solvents.

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